

Usage of Cloud Security Audit Tools among Information System Audit Professionals in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

The increasing reliance on cloud computing has elevated the importance of robust security and compliance frameworks within cloud systems to a prominent area of global research focus. Cloud Security Audit Tools (CSATs) play a crucial role in safeguarding data integrity and regulatory adherence, yet their adoption in Sri Lanka remains limited due to challenges such as inadequate awareness, skill deficiencies, and regulatory uncertainties. This study aims to assess the level of knowledge and expertise among Information System Audit Professionals (ISAPs) in Sri Lanka, their perceptions of global trends in cloud security auditing, and the potential impact of these tools on the auditing profession in both the short and long term. A qualitative research approach was employed, utilizing semi-structured interviews with seven experienced ISAPs. Thematic analysis revealed that while CSATs enhance efficiency, risk assessment, and continuous monitoring, several barriers impede their adoption, including cost constraints, data security concerns, and the lack of structured training programs. Additionally, evolving regulatory requirements present further complexities for organizations seeking to integrate these tools into their audit practices. The findings underscore the need for targeted training initiatives, stronger industry collaboration, and clearer regulatory frameworks to facilitate broader adoption. This study has significant implications for policymakers, organizations, and educators, providing insights into how Sri Lanka can align with global security standards while addressing local challenges. Limitations include a small sample size and geographic scope, suggesting that future research should incorporate larger, more diverse participant groups and conduct comparative studies across different regulatory environments to deepen understanding and drive meaningful advancements in cloud security auditing.

Keywords: *Cloud Security Audit Tools, Information Systems Audit, Regulatory Compliance, Data Security, Global Security Standards*